

LONGITUDINAL AND TRANSVERSAL FLOW MECHANISMS OF THE RESIN IN THE RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING PROCESS AND DETERMINATION OF CHARACTERISTICS FOR THE MODELIZATION

Geoffroy GOULLEY - Sabine EYBERT-BERARD - José PABIOT
Département Technologie des Polymères et Composites
Ecole des Mines de Douai (FRANCE)

ABSTRACT

Short-shot series were made with the RTM process. A fine analysis showed that particular flow phenomena appear (compression of the fiber reinforcement, poor fiber zones, elongated flow front in the thickness) depending on some parameters. Longitudinal and transversal permeability measurement and compression tests can explain these phenomena.

Keywords : RTM ; flow mechanisms ; permeability ; fiber glass compressibility

1. INTRODUCTION

The Resin Transfer Molding (RTM) gives the possibility to make structural parts by injecting a liquid resin through a fibrous reinforcement which has been pre-placed in a mold. This technology is growing and nowadays, the industrial purpose is the modelization of the process. So, flow phenomena have to be understood.

Therefore, as a first step, the Ecole des Mines de Douai in the context of a contract with RENAULT, P.S.A., S.N.P.E. and with the collaboration of CISI INGENIERIE and the CEMEF and LMA laboratories has analyzed some short-shot series showing particular flow phenomena.

As a second step, devices were developed to determine the permeabilities values and compressibility measurements were made to explain the phenomena observed on the short-shots.

2. SHORT-SHOTS ANALYSIS

2.1. Short-shots fabrication

Short-shots were made with a RTM unit and a planar mold with the inlet perpendicular to the plane - Figure 1. The resin was a polyisocyanurate and we used the following fiber glass fabrics :

- mat Unifilo (MA) : 450 g.m⁻²
- unidirectionnal woven fabric (UD) : 420 g.m⁻²
- bidirectionnal woven fabric (BD) : 1740 g.m⁻²
- mixed fabrics (MI) : 1UD/6MA/1UD
2UD/4MA/2UD
3UD/2MA/3UD

2.2. Short-shots analysis

First, recto and verso of the faces were observed. We establish that the resin easily impregnates all the thickness part in the mat but it has difficulties to pass through the woven fabrics - Figure 2.

Short-shots were cut into samples and geometrical measurements were made with a microscope after a polishing. These measures confirmed the good impregnation of the mat and the bad impregnation of the woven fabrics in the thickness. Moreover, the mat always holds all the thickness of the cavity whereas woven fabrics are compressed and rich resin zone appears near the mold wall of the sprue side - Figures 3 and 4.

The propagation of the resin in RTM depends clearly on the permeability and the compressibility of the reinforcement. Then these two parameters have to be studied.

3. PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENTS

3.1. Principle

Mostly, permeability values are obtained from Darcy's law - Equation 1 -, considering a Newtonian fluid in laminar permanent flow :

$$Q = K \cdot \frac{A}{\mu} \cdot \frac{\Delta P}{\Delta L} \quad (1)$$

with Q : flow rate ($m^3 \cdot s^{-1}$) ; K : permeability (m^2) ; A : section of the cavity (m^2) ; μ : viscosity (Pa.s) ; ΔP : pressure drop (Pa) on the distance ΔL (m).

3.2. Mold for the determination of longitudinal permeability

The principle - Figure 5 - of our mold - Figure 6 - is similar to the one used in [1,2]. From flow rate and pressure drop values measured during a steady state flow of a fluid in a parallelepipedic mold fed in one of its extremities, the permeability in the flow direction can be determined with the simple application of Darcy's law.

The feed at one of the mold's extremities is on all its width. Three pressure transducers were mounted amid the six locations of the mold. The flow rate was measured by weighing at the outlet. The injection system is composed of a transfer cylinder driven by a hydraulic cylinder controlled by a proportional distributor in order to have a regular flow rate.

3.3. Apparatus for the determination of the transversal permeability

A special equipment has been developed - Figure 7 - has the same principle. A sample is cut and positioned in the apparatus. The gap for the sample is controlled with a set of adjusting washers between the plug and the body. A pressure transducer is positioned upstream of the sample. The difference between the pressure drop with and without the sample gives the pressure drop due to the sample. A transfer cylinder driven by a dynamometer - Figure 8 - was used to have a constant flow rate. The flow rate is calculated with the movement of the crosshead and the sizes of the cylinder. Very few articles have been published on this subject [3;4].

3.4. Materials

3.4.1. Fluid

The fluid used for the experiments is a plasticizer, its viscosity is 0,1 Pa.s at 20°C. Measures were made in an air-conditioned room.

3.4.2. Reinforcements

The reinforcements are the same as those used in the short-shots (see § 2.1.).

3.5. Results

3.5.1. Methodology

For each pair of pressure transducers we plot the flow rate (Q) versus $(A/\mu \cdot \Delta P / \Delta L)$, so, the permeability is the slope at the origin - Figure 9.

For each tested reinforcement, we also get three permeability values (one for each pair of transducers) from which we calculate the mean.

3.5.2. Results

See - Table 1.

Table 1 : Results	PERMEABILITIES (x 10 ⁻¹² m ²)						RATIO		
	Transversal			Longitudinal			Long./Trans.		
FABRIC	20%	35%	55%	20%	35%	55%	20%	35%	55%
BD		47	10		5000	240		106	24
UDwa		12	2		1000	30		83	15
UDwe		12	2		1000	12		83	6
MA	1344	619		2600	800		2		1
MI1/6/1		165			760				5
MI2/4/2		155			1300				8
MI3/2/3		32			3500				109

We see that the ratio of the longitudinal permeability to the transversal permeability is very high in the case of the woven fabrics. A such anisotropy explains the bad propagation of the resin in these reinforcements.

4. COMPRESSIBILITY MEASUREMENTS

4.1. Materials

These experiments were done with a compression installation on a dynamometer. The stacks tested are the same as those used for the permeability measurements - Figure 10. The sizes of the samples are 100x100.

4.2. Results

Compressibility curves - Figure 11 - show that mats are less compressible than woven fabrics. The resin can also compress the woven reinforcements more easy and create rich resin zones.

5. PROPAGATION MECHANISM

We can propose a propagation mechanism which takes into account the permeabilities and the compressibility of the reinforcements - Figure 12. If we consider a section of two plies of fabric in which the resin comes from above :

- in a ply, the movement of a resin element is proportional to the longitudinal and transversal permeability values.
- when a resin element coming from the upper ply 1 (or from the inlet) and reach the lower ply 2, two cases can occur :
 - . if the resin pressure exceeds the compression level of the fabric 2 (with perhaps a coefficient β), the resin compresses the glass and bastes between the two plies (or between the first

ply and the wall) until equilibrium,

if the resin pressure is less than the fabric compression level, there is no compression of the lower ply 2 and two cases can occur one more time :

+ if the longitudinal permeability of the upper fabric 1 is higher than the transversal permeability of the lower fabric 2 (with perhaps a coefficient α), the resin element will flow longitudinally in the upper fabric.

+ if the longitudinal permeability of the upper ply 1 is less than the transversal permeability of the lower ply 2 (with perhaps a coefficient α), the resin element will enter the lower ply.

6. CONCLUSION

This work has permitted to explain some phenomena of resin propagation observed in short-shots produced with the RTM process with permeability and compressibility measurements. The ratio of the longitudinal permeability to transversal permeability calculated for the mats are lower than those determined for the woven fabrics. This confirms the fact that in woven fabrics, the resin flows with difficulties in the thickness. So, a bidimensional flow software for RTM would simulate accurately only the flow of resin in mats. It couldn't show the difficulties of impregnation in the thickness of reinforcements which contain woven fabrics.

References

1. Gauvin, R., Chibani, M., *The modelling of mold filling in resin transfer molding*, Intern. Polymer Processing, 1986.
2. Lee, L.J., Molnar, J.A., Trevino, L., *Mold filling in SRIM and RTM : controlling a critical processing parameter*, Modern Plastic International, pp. 64-69, 1989.
3. Gutowski, T.G., Boucher, D., Bauer, S., *Consolidation experiments for laminates composites*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 21, pp. 650-669, 1987
4. Lee, L.J., Wang, T.J., Perry, M.J., *Analysis of permeability and void formation in resin transfer molding*, ANTEC, pp. 756-760, 1992.

GENERAL PROCESSING
